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SCIENCE OF EDUCATION

Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction as Correlates of School Organisational Development

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Abstract

The current study examines the relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction, focusing on their collective influence on school organizational development. It further investigates the mediating role of job satisfaction in a school setting. This study adopted a quantitative research design which implores correlational and mediation approaches. Using SPSS PROCESS macro, data for 236 school employees collected using purposive sampling technique was then analyzed. Results revealed transformational leadership, job satisfaction and organizational development were all significantly positively correlated to each other. Further findings revealed job satisfaction partially mediated the link between transformational leadership and school organizational development. These findings suggest that in a school setting, transformational leadership practices and employees job satisfaction are critically vital constructs that promotes school organizational development. It was recommended that secondary and high school leaders should adopt transformational leadership practices, ensure positive levels of employees' job satisfaction which in turn will create a positive school environment.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, job satisfaction, organizational development, school employees, mediation analysis

1. Introduction

Transformational leadership has the power to reshape followers' expectations, demands, thoughts, and overall awareness. This leadership style enables leaders to inspire their teams to prioritize the organization's success and benefits above individual interests (Phuket, 2009; Rijal, 2016). Transformational leadership is a style that motivates and empowers people to achieve more and improve both themselves and their organization's operations. This approach encourages followers to take ownership of their tasks and responsibilities (Koehler & Pankowski, 1997).

Across the globe, organizations have been compelled to adapt to rapid shifts in politics, economics, society, and especially technology. This continuous adaptation, aligned with an organization's strategic plan, is vital for its survival (Lawler & Worley, 2006). Constant change and improvement are essential; without them, any organization will inevitably decline and fail, much like living organisms (Intakarn, 2013; Pandla, 2016). In this dynamic

environment, transformational leadership stands out as a crucial executive trait. It effectively persuades personnel to focus on the organization's overarching vision and goals, fostering enthusiasm and encouraging them to embrace work challenges collectively.

In Cameroon, a study by National Institute of Statistics pointed to the importance of human capital—including education, training, experience, age, and sex (National Institute of Statistics, 2009). Other field research reveals significant gaps in leadership skills (like entrepreneurship, management, and wealth creation) among those managing small and medium-sized educational businesses in Yaoundé. Essentially, many CEOs, administrators, and staff in these small education enterprises reported having a university education, but without relevant entrepreneurship training (Teneng, 2020).

The entire education system's success relies on the dedication of principals (secondary school head teachers), headmasters, administrators, teachers, and support staff—the school's core strength. School organization as the core of national education is dependent on the leadership management and members of the organization to achieve progress. Many previous studies on schools' management found that schools that achieve high success in academics is led by the principal/headmaster who has the qualities of effective leadership (Pont, 2014; Harris et al., 2013; Ibrahim & Wahab, 2012; Harris & Chapman, 2002; Marzuk, 1997; Mortimore, 1995). Commitment of teachers towards the tasks entrusted to them start with the comfort and enjoyment of their work. All their actions are attributable to a number of factors that make the existence of an atmosphere and work environment in schools including approach to leadership in school management.

A transformational leader, according to Aydin et al. (2013), prioritizes positive relationships with employees, ensuring fair and equitable treatment. They offer support and guidance, and actively encourage staff development by involving them in decision-making. Such leaders are also deeply committed to achieving established goals and visions. A study found that transformational leadership leads to staff working effectively in teams. Leaders under this style dedicate time to building relationships and create opportunities for staff to contribute to the school's success, ultimately boosting student achievement (Abdullah, 2009). Meanwhile, Sulan (2008) highlighted that teacher job satisfaction is strongly linked to teacher effectiveness, which in turn contributes to student achievement. This underscores that fostering job satisfaction is a critical success factor for any school.

In contemporary educational settings, the role of leadership and job satisfaction in shaping school organizational development has become increasingly critical. Transformational leadership, characterized by inspiring and motivating teachers, fostering a sense of shared vision, and promoting personal and professional growth, is widely believed to influence the overall effectiveness and development of schools. However, despite the growing recognition of transformational leadership's significance, there is limited empirical evidence that

explicitly connects transformational leadership practices with teachers' job satisfaction and, in turn, the broader organizational development within schools.

Teachers' job satisfaction, which encompasses the level of contentment and fulfillment teachers feel about their roles, is a critical factor influencing both individual performance and the collective functioning of schools. However, in Cameroon some teachers still turn to abandon their jobs and travel abroad. (Education International, 2024). This calls for the need to investigate level of school employees' job satisfaction.

School organizational development, a continuous process of improving the effectiveness of a school's systems, structures, culture, and people, is essential for ensuring the school's long-term success and adaptability. As schools face dynamic challenges, the link between leadership, teacher satisfaction, and organizational growth becomes even more pertinent (Knoff, 2007).

This study seeks to explore the correlation between transformational leadership and school employees' job satisfaction and how these two factors collectively contribute to school organizational development. Understanding this relationship can offer valuable insights for school leaders, policymakers, and educational stakeholders aiming to foster environments where both teachers and students can thrive. The key question guiding this research is: How does transformational leadership influence school employees' job satisfaction, and in what ways do these factors contribute to the overall organizational development of schools?

This investigation aims to fill the gap in the literature regarding the interconnectedness of leadership practices, teacher satisfaction, and school development, providing practical implications for enhancing school performance and organizational effectiveness. Therefore, based on this backdrop, the current study aims to specifically investigate; 1) how transformational leadership is related to school employees' job satisfaction, 2) the relationship between transformational leadership and school organizational development, 3) how school employees' job satisfaction relates to school organizational development, and 4) Mediating role of school employees' job satisfaction.

The significance of studying *transformational leadership* and *employees' job satisfaction* as correlates of *school organizational development* is profound, as it helps to understand how leadership practices and teacher well-being contribute to the overall effectiveness and progress of educational institutions. This study is significant for several reasons that includes all stakeholders of the school system.

Firstly, the study leads to *enhancement of School Leadership Practices*- where transformational leadership which, emphasizes inspiration, motivation, and intellectual stimulation, has been shown to positively affect teacher performance, engagement, and morale (Andriani et al., 2018). By studying this, educational leaders can develop leadership styles that better foster a supportive and productive work environment (Etomes et al., 2024). Understanding this

relationship helps identify the best leadership practices that enhance the overall development of the school, improving decision-making processes and aligning school objectives with teachers' goals.

Secondly, this study is significant as it helps in *improving employees' job satisfaction*: Job satisfaction is directly linked to teacher retention, motivation, and commitment. Additionally, a positive work environment created by transformational leaders can reduce burnout, absenteeism, and turnover rates among teachers, all of which are crucial for maintaining school stability and development (Ewane, 2022).

Another significance of the current study is that it will foster organizational development as School organizational development focuses on improving the overall structure, culture, and processes of the institution. The study provides insights into how leadership styles and teacher job satisfaction influence the development of the school's organizational culture and long-term progress. More also, effective leadership contributes to the creation of a collaborative environment where teachers feel valued and empowered, promoting a culture of continuous learning and improvement within the school (Ashu et al., 2021).

In addition, the current study will have positive impact on students' outcomes. Such as when teachers are satisfied and motivated by transformational leadership, their performance improves, which directly benefits students. This, in turn, contributes to better academic outcomes, student engagement, and overall school success. The study can show how improving the work environment for teachers can indirectly affect students' educational experiences, contributing to a positive cycle of development (Michaelowa, 2002).

Lastly, the study will be useful to policy makers by guiding policy and decision-making, as the findings of this study can inform policymakers, school administrators, and educational researchers about the importance of supporting teachers through effective leadership and job satisfaction. This can lead to better policies that foster a more collaborative and nurturing school environment. Similarly, the research can influence decisions on leadership training programs, teacher retention strategies, and professional development initiatives aimed at improving school Organizational Outcomes.

2. Literature Review

In this section, we present the theories which the current study is/are rooted upon and also present the related studies with respect to the specific objectives.

2.1. Theoretical framework

Transformational Leadership Theory (Bass, 1985)

Transformational leadership is defined by Bass (1985) as a leadership style in which leaders work with teams to identify needed change, creating a vision to guide that change, and executing the change in tandem with committed members of the group. In the context of education, transformational leaders inspire and motivate teachers, encourage innovation, and foster an environment of trust and support.

Transformational leaders inspire their teams to embrace innovative ideas and envision new possibilities that drive organizational growth and success. They cultivate a strong sense of dedication, enthusiasm, and loyalty among their managers and staff. This empowers the organization's members to implement significant changes at its core, building the essential capabilities needed to navigate new paths and achieve ambitious performance goals (Mirkamali et al., 2014). This theory is critical in this study for it depicts the importance of transformational leadership with key areas such as 1) *Idealized Influence*- where Leaders act as role models, inspiring respect and admiration; 2) *Inspirational Motivation*- where leaders motivate others by providing a compelling vision; 3) *Intellectual Stimulation*- where leaders encourage creativity and problem-solving among followers; and 4) *individualized consideration*- where leaders provide personalized support to teachers.

Maslow's Theory (1954)

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs was adopted for this study to ground the concept of job satisfaction. Maslow's Theory proposed in 1954, posits that humans have fundamental needs (figure 1) that drive their satisfaction (Norazmi et al., 2019). Maslow's hierarchy of needs categorizes human needs into two main groups: deficiency needs and growth needs. He argued that within the deficiency needs, each lower-level need must be satisfied before an individual can progress to the next higher level. If a previously met deficiency need re-emerges, the person will instinctively work to fulfill it again. The four initial deficiency levels are: 1) *Physiological Needs*: Basic survival necessities like hunger, thirst, and physical Comfort; 2) *Safety/Security Needs*: The need to feel protected and out of harm's way; 3) *Belongingness and Love Needs*: The desire to connect with others and feel accepted; and 4) *Esteem Needs*: The drive for achievement, competence, approval, and recognition (Maslow, 1954)

Meeting these basic needs is crucial for achieving self-actualization; conversely, unmet needs can lead to inner turmoil and hinder personal and professional fulfillment (Firkhan et al., 2021).

Source: RLI-Rotary Leadership Institute (2018)

Figure 1: *Maslow Hierarchy of Needs*

Job satisfaction as drawn from Maslow's` Hierarchy of needs and related research, is the degree to which teachers feel content and fulfilled with various aspects of their job. Some factors influencing job satisfaction include: *work environment* which involves school climate, collegiality, leadership support, and resources; *teacher autonomy* - which is the ability to make decisions and influence educational practices; *professional development* which involves the opportunities for growth and advancement; and lastly *Work-life balance*: - which is the ability to maintain a healthy balance between work and personal life (Maslow, 1954).

Organizational Development Theory (Burke, 1976)

Expanding on the theory of Friedlander and Brown (1974) who grouped socio-technical approaches with "techno-structural approaches," which, in their view, focused on organizational structures and technology, in contrast to "human processual approaches" that dealt with people and processes, Burke (1976), a keen observer of the field, noted a significant shift in organizational development, suggesting it might eventually be known as Quality of Work Intervention (QWI) or Quality of Working Life (QWL). He described a key transition where the practitioner's role expanded from primarily working with management to engaging with both managers and employees at all organizational levels. This evolution in organizational development means practitioners must now focus much more on socio-technical systems, human engineering, job design, and ultimately, improving the overall quality of working life.

Thus, Organizational Development (OD) in schools refers to planned efforts to improve the effectiveness of the school system, focusing on factors like: *school culture and climate*-involving shared values, beliefs, and behaviors that define the school environment; *school structure*- which is the design of roles, responsibilities, and relationships within the school; and *continuous improvement* - which is the systematic approach to improving teaching, learning, and overall performance (Burke, 1976).

This theory is critical in this study as a transformational leadership style contributes to organizational development by fostering a supportive climate where teachers feel valued and engaged. Teachers' job satisfaction, in turn, positively influences the performance and effectiveness of the school.

2.2. Conceptual Framework

In this sub-section, literature with respect to the relationships among the constructs are presented. Accordingly; relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction, then, the relation between transformational leadership and school organizational development, followed by the relation between teachers' job satisfaction and school organizational development, and lastly, mediation role of teachers' job satisfaction.

Relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction

The concept of transformational leadership and job satisfaction of teachers' in a school setting is not new. Modern research largely agrees that successful organizations and effective schools are led by individuals who create environments where employees feel satisfied (Adams & Bailey, 1989; Kouni et al., 2018). In fact, ensuring employee satisfaction is now considered a top priority for organizational leaders (Aydin et al., 2013). This understanding has fueled continuous research into the connection between leadership and job satisfaction, an area that remains of significant interest to scholars.

Studies consistently show a strong link between transformational leadership and teacher job satisfaction (Jeyashuma et al., 2017; Aydin et al., 2013; Leithwood & Sun, 2012). For instance, a 2016 survey of 387 Iranian teachers in 42 schools found that the relationship between principals and teachers acts as both an external and internal motivator for increased job satisfaction. Teachers' trust in their principal's judgment and values, coupled with the school's mission, creates an emotional connection to leadership that boosts job satisfaction (Sayadi, 2016). Similarly, Tesfaw (2014) in a survey of 320 Ethiopian secondary school teachers in 20 schools revealed that transformational principals' behavior strongly correlated with teacher job satisfaction. A charismatic transformational principal can serve as a role model, earning teachers' admiration and trust, and fostering two-way communication and a shared commitment to school goals.

Within the context of Cameroon, few studies have directly investigated the relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction in the school settings. However,

very interesting findings were reported. For instance, Lyonga (2019) in a study conducted with 100 secondary school teachers using four secondary schools in Kumba II Municipality (Cameroon), reported that transformational leadership is key to boosting teacher job satisfaction and school effectiveness. This is linked to an effective leadership style that can transform teachers' perceptions and motivation, leading to greater job satisfaction and overall school excellence. Similarly, Sylvain (2024) using 656 teachers` in Mfoundi Division (Centre region) of Cameroon, found out that transformational leadership positively impacts employee job satisfaction in private secondary schools. In contrast, in public secondary schools within Mfoundi Division in the Centre region of Cameroon, both transactional and laissez-faire leadership styles were linked to increased job satisfaction. It's important to note, however, that laissez-faire leadership was also found to be detrimental to both employee job satisfaction and overall productivity.

H1: Transformational Leadership will be positively correlate with job satisfaction

Relationship between Transformational leadership and school organizational development.

Research consistently demonstrates a strong link between transformational leadership and organizational progress (Chou et al., 2013; Choudhary and Zaheer, 2013; Sehrawat and Sharma, 2014; Birasnav, 2014; Hamstra et al., 2011; Lewis et al., 2017). This connection likely stems from transformational leaders' focus on both organizational goals and individual aspirations. Transformational leadership fosters a positive environment of change and advancement, which in turn helps an organization grow. By assisting employees in finding meaning and significance in their work, these leaders can make staff feel supported by their organization. This sense of support often encourages employees to exert extra effort (Walumbwa et al., 2013; Li et al., 2019).

Cameroon is a good example in higher education reforms within Sub-Saharan Africa, aiming to address the economy's human capital requirements. According to Law No. 005 of April 16, 2001, which structures higher education, it encompasses all post-secondary training offered by both state-run and approved private institutions. Article 2 of this law outlines Higher education's core mission: to generate, organize, and share scientific, cultural, professional, and ethical knowledge for developmental purposes. This reinforces the idea that higher education institutions are key players in knowledge production. Achieving the goals of higher education hinges on effective governance policies, and continuously reforming these policies to adapt to a changing environment is essential for the system's long-term sustainability (Cameroon, 2001).

In line with these reforms, some researchers in Cameroon have reported evidence of significant relation between transformational leadership and school organizational development in part. For instance, Etome et al. (2024) in a study with 2745 teachers (state -

1692 & private - 1053) in some universities across 7 regions out of 10 in Cameroon, reported that transformational leadership was significantly positively correlated to sustainable productivity in higher education institutes in Cameroon. Another study which investigated relation between leadership styles and school organizational performance of 345 employees in some primary and secondary schools in Cameroon, reported transformational leadership as a significant predictor of school organizational performance (Salamine & Rodrigue, 2020).

Amongst the literature within Cameroon observed, none has investigated the direct relationship between transformational leadership and overall school organizational development, wherein the current study tries to bridge this gap by formatting the following hypothesis;

H2: Transformational leadership will significantly positively correlate with school organizational development

Relationship between job satisfaction and school organizational development

Literature on the relationship between job satisfaction and school organizational development is scarce as most researchers in this domain have addressed specific aspects of school organizational development. However, some evidence of the relationship between teachers' job satisfaction and some determinants of school organizational development are presented herein. Job satisfaction is vital for an organization's success, as a strong link exists between it and work performance (Usop et al., 2013). High employee satisfaction is crucial for an organization to function effectively and reach its goals. Similarly, in education, teacher job satisfaction is paramount for a school's successful operation. It has been shown to have a positive and significant impact on teaching efficacy (Collie et al., 2012) and even on student learning (Michaelowa, 2002), and school effectiveness (Somech et al., 2000).

Iwu et al. (2013) in a study with 279 educators in selected high schools in Western Cape province of South Africa, reported that educators with high levels of motivation were significantly associated to high levels of job satisfaction and high levels of learner performance, compared to their counterparts with low level of job satisfaction. Essentially, the quality of teaching and learning in rural areas is often compromised, which can negatively affect student pass rates (Bhorat & Oosthuizen, 2006). For example, a South African study by Naidoo et al. (2013) identified several factors contributing to teacher job dissatisfaction, including excessive workload, limited opportunities for professional growth, job insecurity, and a lack of autonomy. Similarly, Mji and Makgato (2006) linked teacher demotivation to poor academic performance among high school students, suggesting a deficit in essential teacher qualities. All these can affect the overall school climate.

Thus, reviewing the literature addressing the direct relationship between teachers' job satisfaction and school organizational climate in Cameroon showed significant gap, as most researchers in this domain did not investigate this direct relationship in school settings. For

instance, significant improvement of the internal organization in the health sector like purchase of new equipment', was associated to high levels of job satisfaction of employees (Manga et al., 2018). Additionally, higher level of employee's job satisfaction was significantly associated to higher levels of employee performance in small and medium size enterprises (Fokam & Ngoata, 2022). Based on this huge gap in the literature the following hypothesis was proposed.

H3: Teachers job satisfaction will be significantly positively associated with school organizational development.

Mediating role of Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction as a mediator constructs in the relationship between transformational leadership and school organizational development is the uniqueness of the current study. In review of the literature no empirical study has investigated this mediating role in the current context in Cameroon and beyond. However, the role of teachers' job satisfaction as a mediator is not new. For instance, Nwosu et al. (2024) in a study with 502 teachers in Anambra State in Nigeria, provided evidence that teachers job satisfaction mediated the relationship between tolerance of frustration and their inclusive education willingness. Another study by Ali et al. (2016) with 80 teachers amongst some selected secondary schools in Mogadishu - Somalia, reported that teachers' job satisfaction significantly mediated the relationship between teacher motivation and school performance. The significance of teachers' job satisfaction in education settings is critical. Thus, based on the gap in the literature of job satisfaction as a mediator construct in the relation between transformational leadership and job satisfaction, the current study proposes the following hypothesis.

H4: Teachers' job satisfaction mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and school organizational development.

Figure 2: Conceptual diagram

The Research model adopted for this study is shown in figure 2. Based on the hypotheses presented, the model shows school organizational development as the main dependent variable, while transformational leadership is the main independent variable with job satisfaction as mediating variable.

3. Method

Study design

This study employed a cross-sectional quantitative survey design to collect data from employees at some selected bilingual academic institutions in Cameroon, specifically in the cities of Yaoundé and Dschang, selected purposely for convenience. Study population included all bilingual private and public secondary and high schools in Dschang and Yaounde. The participants, totaling 236 volunteers were selected using purposive sampling, included teachers, school administrators, drivers, secretaries, and security personnel from selected private and public secondary and high schools. Their participation was voluntary.

Paper questionnaires were distributed to participants via school administrators. The researchers clearly explained the purpose of the study and assured participants of data confidentiality. Participants were given one week to complete the questionnaires at their convenience and return them. The questionnaires gathered socio-demographic information about the employees, as well as their self-reported experiences related to transformational leadership, job satisfaction and organizational development.

Participants

A total of 236 employees took part in this survey. Eligibility criteria for participation was to be an employee in any private or public secondary or high school in either Dschang or Yaounde. The characteristics of the employee - participants are presented in table 1. Participants involved 159 teachers (67.2%), 33 secretaries (14%), 14 drivers (5.9%), 23 school administrators (9.7%), and 7 securities (3%).

According to gender, there were more female participants (122) than male participants (114) representing 51.7% and 48.3% respectively. With respect to age, majority of the respondents (61.4%) were between the ages of 26 to 35 years old. Data showed that 42.4% employees were holders of Bachelor degree or its equivalent, 20.3% were Masters' degree holders, 2.6% were Doctorate degree holders, 29.1% of them were holders of high school diploma, and 7.6% of the participants had less than high school diploma. For academic institutions, majority of the respondents belong to public high schools (46.6%), followed by those belonging to public secondary schools (32.2%), while private secondary and high schools' participants were 11% and 10.2% respectively. Overall, five schools participated in this study. Accordingly, majority of participants (46.6%) were from Government Bilingual High School Mendong, followed by 'Lycee' Bilingue De Dschang (19.5%).

Table 1: Characteristics of participants

Constructs	Sub-category	n	%
Gender	Male	114	48.3
	Female	122	51.7
Age	Less than 25 years	26	11.0
	25 - 35 years	145	61.4
	36 - 45 years	56	23.7
	46-55 years	7	3.0
	Above 55 years	2	0.9
Education level	Less than High school diploma	18	7.6
	High school diploma	64	29.1
	Bachelor degree/equivalent	100	42.4
	Masters` degree	48	20.3
	PhD/equivalent	6	2.6
	Job title	Teacher	159
	Secretary	33	14.0
	Driver	14	5.9
	School administrator	23	9.7
	Security	7	3.0
School type	Public secondary school	76	32.2
	Public high school	110	46.6

	Private secondary school	24	10.2
	Private high school	26	11
	Government Classical	30	12.7
	High School Dschang		
Schools	'Lycee bilingue De Dschang'	46	19.5
	'College private De L'Ouest'	24	10.2
	Government Bilingual High School Mendong-Yaounde	110	46.6
	Kamgai international bilingual secondary school- Yaounde	26	11

Source: Fieldwork 2024

Measures

We assessed transformational leadership using the Global Transformational Leadership Scale (GTLS), a 7-item questionnaire developed by Carless et al. (2000). This scale has proven to be both highly reliable and valid. Participants rated statements, such as "leaders communicate a clear positive vision of the future," on a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 meant "to a very small extent" and 5 meant "to a very large extent." Scores for individual items were added up to get a total transformational leadership score, ranging from a minimum of 7 points to a maximum of 35 points. Higher scores indicated a greater degree of transformational leadership. In this study, the GTLS demonstrated good reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha (α) of 0.746.

We measured employee job satisfaction using the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ), developed by the University of Minnesota and adapted from Weiss et al. (1967). This 20-item questionnaire assesses employees' satisfaction with their jobs using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "1 = not satisfied" to "5 = extremely satisfied." An example item is "your leaders try to get your ideas." To get a total job satisfaction score, all individual item scores are summed. Scores can range from a minimum of 20 points to a maximum of 100 points, with higher scores indicating greater job satisfaction. In this study, the MSQ demonstrated good reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha (α) of 0.828.

Lastly, to assess organizational development, this study utilized the School Organizational Development Questionnaire (SODQ), adapted from Mullen (1974). The SODQ is a comprehensive 44-item questionnaire broken down into five sub-categories: Leadership process (12 items), Interaction process (7 items), Decision-making process (11 items), Control

process (5 items), and Communication process (9 items). A sample item is: "teamwork is used to improve things."

Participants responded on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "1 = strongly disagree" to "5 = strongly agree." The total organizational development score is the sum of scores across all sub-categories, with a possible range from 44 points (lowest) to 220 points (highest). Higher scores indicate more positive organizational development, while lower scores suggest negative development. The SODQ demonstrated good reliability in this study, with a Cronbach's alpha (α) of 0.895.

Data analysis

The study's data was analyzed using SPSS PROCESS macro (Hayes, 2018). Before the main analysis, negative survey items were reverse-coded, and all continuous variables were mean-centered. Preliminary tests confirmed the reliability and validity of the research tools, with all constructs demonstrating good standing, as detailed in Table 2. SPSS was used to conduct frequency analysis, descriptive statistics, and correlation analysis.

Table 2: Cronbach alpha and internal consistency for main/sub constructs

Main constructs	Cronbach alpha (α)	Harman's single factor test (CMV)
Transformational leadership (TL)	0.746	
Job Satisfaction (JS)	0.828	16.540%
Organizational development (OD)	0.895	

CMV: *Common Method Variance*.

Mediation analysis was performed using SPSS PROCESS macro with bootstrapping. For all analyses, effects were considered statistically significant if at 95% confidence intervals, derived from 5,000 corrected bootstrap samples, did not include zero between their lower and upper limits.

4. Results

The results of the current study are presented in order of objectives/hypothesis. Firstly, descriptive statistics is presented as preliminary findings to get an insight of the data. Then results according to specific objectives are presented and interpreted.

Descriptive statistics (Preliminary findings).

As glean on table 3, In order to describe the main and sub constructs, descriptive statistics was performed.

Looking at the main constructs, on a scale of 1 to 5, the perceptions of employees averaged as follows: Transformational leadership had a mean of 3.173 (SD = 0.752), which translates to approximately 22.211 out of 35 points. This indicates that transformational leadership was perceived as being practiced to a moderate extent. Organizational development had a mean of 3.317 (SD = 0.487) and job satisfaction had a mean of 2.946 (SD = 0.594). Overall, Table 3 shows that participants reported organizational development and job satisfaction was perceived to a moderate extent (see fig2a).

Table 3: *Descriptive statistics*

Variable	sub-categories	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Skewness		kurtosis	
					Stats	Error	Stats	error
Transformational leadership (TL)	=>	236	3.173	0.752	0.014	0.158	-0.377	0.312
	=>	236	3.317	0.487	0.601	0.158	0.830	0.312
Organizational Development (OD)	LP	236	3.179	0.645	-0.117	0.158	0.240	0.312
	IP	236	3.477	0.629	-0.280	0.158	1.372	0.312
	DMP	236	3.277	0.545	-0.096	0.158	0.739	0.312
	CP	236	3.460	0.663	0.056	0.158	-0.128	0.312
	ComP	236	3.189	0.699	0.270	0.158	-0.012	0.312
Job Satisfaction (JS)	=>	236	2.946	0.594	0.496	0.158	0.053	0.312

Source: authors. LP: Leadership process; IP: Interactive process; DMP: Decision making process; CP: Control process; ComP: Communication process

With respect to the sub - constructs, for organizational development, the interactive process (M = 3.477, SD = 0.629) and control process (M = 3.460, SD = 0.663) showed higher mean values. In contrast, leadership process (M = 3.179, SD = 0.645), decision-making process (M = 3.277, SD = 0.545), and communication process (M = 3.189, SD = 0.699) had comparatively lower means (see fig.2b).

As Table 3 shows, the data points were normally distributed. This was determined because all absolute skewness values were less than 3, and all absolute kurtosis values were less than 7, consistent with guidelines of standard normal distribution (George & Mallery, 2010; Byrne 2013).

OD: organizational development; JS: Job satisfaction;

TL: Transformational Leadership

Figure 2a: Mean of Main Constructs

Figure 2b: Mean of OD determinants

Results according specific objectives 1, 2 & 3 (H1, H2 & H3)

Correlation analysis

In order to investigate the relationships amongst transformational leadership, job satisfaction, and organizational development in a school setting, Pearson correlation analysis was used since preliminary findings revealed the data was normally distributed. The correlation results are presented in table 4.

Table 4: Correlation of main constructs

Constructs	1(TL)	2(JS)	3(OD)
1. Transformational leadership (TL)	1		
2. Job satisfaction (JS)	0.423***	1	
3. Organizational development (OD)	0.495***	0.596***	1

Source: authors. *** $p < 0.001$

As showed in table 4, transformational leadership (TL) was statistically significantly; positively correlated to job satisfaction -JS ($r = 0.423^{***}$), and positively correlated to organizational development-OD ($r = 0.495^{***}$). Similarly, job satisfaction was statistically significantly; positively correlated to organizational development ($r = 0.596^{***}$).

Accordingly, regarding objective one, correlation analysis revealed that transformational leadership is significantly positively correlated to employee’s job satisfaction at 99.9%

confidence level. This indicates that schools with leaders who practiced good levels of transformational leadership traits were associated with high levels of employee's job satisfaction. In other words, low levels of transformational leadership were associated with low levels of employee's job satisfaction (see figure 3a). (*H1 accepted*).

Figure 3a: Relation between TL and JS

Figure 3b: Relation between TL and OD

Figure 3c: Relation between JS and OD

Similarly, regarding specific objective two (or Hypothesis 2), the current findings revealed that transformation leadership is significantly positively related to school organizational development. In other words, high levels of transformational leadership practices (idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation & individual consideration) is significantly associated with high extent of organizational development (see Fig. 3b). Therefore, *H2 is accepted*.

Lastly, the relationship between employees' job satisfaction and organizational development in a school setting reported significant evidence that the more school employees are satisfied with their jobs the more the organizational develops. In other words, school employees with

low levels of job satisfaction were associated with low levels of school organizational development. Therefore, *H3 is accepted*. (See Fig. 3c).

Mediation effect of Job satisfaction (Specific objective 4 - H4)

In order to investigate if job satisfaction plays a mediating role in the relation between transformational leadership and job satisfaction, *Mediation analysis* was performed. Accordingly, the mediating effect was verified.

Prior to conducting the mediation analysis, we control for all demographic characteristics (age, gender, etc.). Using ordinary least squares path analysis, mediation analysis provided evidence that in a school setting, transformational leadership indirectly influences school organizational development through its effect on employees' job satisfaction. Either glean from figure 4a or from table 4, controlling for job satisfaction, transformational leadership showed a significant direct positive influence on school organizational development ($\beta=0.296$, $p<0.001$). Furthermore, transformational leadership showed a significant positive influence on employees' job satisfaction ($\beta=0.423$, $p<0.001$). Additionally, employees job satisfaction was evident to positively influence school organizational development ($\beta=0.471$, $p<0.001$) when controlling for transformational leadership. All effects were observed to be statistically significant at 99.9% confidence level. Looking at the final model, both antecedent constructs (transformational leadership & job satisfaction) explained 42.7% of the variance in school organizational development.

Figure 4a: Statistical Model

Figure 4b: Total effect Model

Figure 4: Statistical Model

development. The employees surveyed reported that their schools' administrators practice transformational leadership to a moderate extent, that their organizations are experiencing moderate development, and that their own job satisfaction is at a moderate level. Based on these findings, for school leaders; the moderate level of transformational leadership suggests a need for improvement, and school administrators should focus on enhancing their skills in innovative thinking, executing a clear vision, developing their staff, empowering employees, and acting as positive role models. Similarly, for school stakeholders; the moderate level of job satisfaction indicates that leaders and board members should implement strategies to improve employee well-being, particularly their job satisfaction. Additionally, stakeholders like the Ministry of Secondary Education in Cameroon should collaborate to ensure a higher level of organizational development in secondary and high schools. Accordingly, the results with respect to the research objectives are discussed;

Regarding research objective one (or Hypothesis one), which investigates the relationship between transformational leadership and employees' job satisfaction, the current study provided evidence of a significant positive relationship. In other words, leaders who exhibit transformational qualities are more likely to create a positive, supportive environment where teachers feel motivated and valued. This, in turn, increases job satisfaction. This result is consistent with previous studies. For example, a recent study carried out in South Western Nigeria with high school principals and teachers reported that school administrators who practiced high level of transformational leadership practices were strongly associated with high level of teachers' job satisfaction (Adeoye, 2025). Similarly, Purwanto (2020) in a study with 127 teachers in selected secondary schools in Indonesia asserted that transformational leadership had a significant positive influence on secondary school teachers' level of job satisfaction. This significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and employees' job satisfaction is of critical importance to secondary and high schools in Cameroon. Creating a school environment that encourages high levels of transformational leadership practices with excellent strategies to ensure employees' high level of job satisfaction will produce excellent school outcomes.

According to research objective two (or hypothesis 2) which examines the relationship between transformational leadership and school organizational development, the current findings reported strong evidence of a significant positive relationship. This positive relation suggests that by encouraging a shared vision, fostering innovation, and providing individualized support, transformational leaders can shape school culture and lead to systemic changes that promote school development. In other words, this indicates that, within the school organizations we studied, the transformational leadership style was a good match for the level of development the organization was able to achieve. Empirical findings that investigates the relation of transformational leadership and school organization development in Cameroon are scarce, which is one of the main originalities of the current study. However, from global perspective, a study among principals and

managers of selected secondary schools in Iran found out that higher levels of transformational leadership were associated to higher levels of school organizational innovations (Rad et al., 2021). Similarly, in other institutional settings like business, there is evidence of significant positive association between transformational leadership and organizational development (Pimonratanakan et al., 2017; Radi et al., 2022).

It is very necessary for decision makers (Cameroon Ministry of Secondary Education) for secondary schools in Cameroon to encourage and train transformational leaders as they have the ability to inspire employees to work harder and grasp the value of organizational development initiatives.

With respect to research question three (or hypothesis 3), which examines the relation between school employees job satisfaction and school organizational development, there was evidence that school employees job satisfaction is significantly positively correlated to organizational development. In other words, the more employees are satisfied with their job the more they contribute to organizational growth. This finding further suggests that the extent of job satisfaction by school employees of this study was positive enough to show their support to their leaders in the leadership process, strong support to their leaders in terms of decision-making process, good liaison in terms of interactive process, and communication process, which are all significant school organizational development practices. It is important to understand that an organization where the leader shares vision, promotes employee development, creates and encourage interaction with employees will create a positive organizational environment that promotes school growth as all employees irrespective of their ranks work together towards achieving the goals of the organization. The positive relation between school employees' job satisfaction and organizational development has strong empirical support globally, though maybe limited within the Cameroon context. For instance, Crisci et al. (2019) asserted significant role of teachers' job satisfaction in improving, developing and reorganizing school activities to enhance organizational growth. Additionally, in part, another study in some selected secondary schools in Indonesia established teachers' job satisfaction is significantly positively associated to school performance and school commitment (Werang et al., 2017).

Lastly, regarding research objective four (or hypothesis 4) which investigates the mediating role of employees' job satisfaction in the relation between transformational leadership and organizational development, the current study found strong evidence of partial mediation. The significant mediating role of school employees job satisfaction suggest the critical need for teachers', school administrators, and other school employees to be highly satisfied with their job as it further enhances the positive influence of transformational leadership on school organizational development. In other words, having school administrators who encourages shared visions, promote employee development, will lead to satisfied

employees' who will in turn tend to be more engaged, innovative, and collaborative, contributing to the improvement and development of the school as an organization.

The use of school employees job satisfaction as a mediator in the relation between transformational leadership is the main strength (uniqueness) of the current study as no research has been carried out specifically addressing the current interplay of the study variables. However, the use of job satisfaction as an intervention construct is strongly backed by literature in the school setting. For instance, Abdul et al. (2021) in a study with 381 school teachers in some selected schools in Malaysia, asserted significant partial mediation of teachers' job satisfaction in the negative link between passive-avoidant leadership styles with teachers' commitment to their organization. Abdul and colleagues also provided evidence that teachers' job satisfaction fully mediated the link between transaction leadership style and organizational commitment among teachers. Therefore, secondary school policy makers, school leaders and other school board, should encourage high level of employees' job satisfaction in line with organization goals to further enhance organizational development.

The main limitation of the current study is the status cross-sectional design which limits investigation about changes that may occur with time. Therefore, future study in this area should employ longitudinal design.

Conclusion

The findings of the current study are summarized and presented herein. However, it is important to point out some important information gathered through this research process. While reviewing the related literatures, researchers found out that huge gaps in the interplay of the constructs as presented in the current study; such as using transformational leadership and employees' job satisfaction as correlates of organizational development in a school setting. However, the current study tries to fill this gap and add more knowledge to existing literature on predictors or correlates of school organizational development. Thus, the findings of the current study are summarized: School leaders with high levels of transformational leadership practices were strongly associated with high levels of employees job satisfaction; transformational leadership is significantly positively correlated to school organizational development; employees' job satisfaction is significantly positively correlated to organizational development; and lastly, job satisfaction of school employees partially mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational development. Therefore, transformational leadership and employees' job satisfaction are critically vital constructs that promotes school organizational development.

Implications of the study

As implication, the current study will promote teacher development and professional growth, as transformational leadership encourages teachers to develop professionally,

fostering an environment that values innovation, critical thinking, and learning. Teachers who feel satisfied with their job are more likely to engage in professional development, which can positively affect school performance (Mpako, 2015). The study can help identify how school leaders can create opportunities for teachers to grow, both professionally and personally, which in turn enhances overall organizational development.

Further implication of the current study is that it will foster organizational development as School organizational development focuses on improving the overall structure, culture, and processes of the institution. The study provides insights into how leadership styles and teacher job satisfaction influence the development of the school's organizational culture and long-term progress. More also, effective leadership contributes to the creation of a collaborative environment where teachers feel valued and empowered, promoting a culture of continuous learning and improvement within the school (Ashu et al., 2021).

Theoretical Implications

Transformational leadership theory suggests that the behavior and practices of school leaders play a crucial role in shaping the school climate, which directly impacts teachers' job satisfaction. The framework builds on existing research that links teacher satisfaction to organizational success, reinforcing the idea that positive leadership leads to engaged, motivated, and satisfied teachers, who in turn contribute to school development.

This theoretical framework can guide empirical research into how leadership practices impact teacher outcomes and broader organizational goals in educational settings. It emphasizes the interrelationship between leadership, employee job satisfaction, and the overall health and development of the school as an organization.

Recommendations

For secondary and high school administrators, based on the current findings, it is recommended that they should adopt transformational leadership practices as it is evident to create a positive school climate. Secondly, school administrators should adopt a strategy to enhance employee job satisfaction as the current study provides evidence that school employees who are satisfied with their jobs in turn perceived positive school development.

Suggestion for further studies

Future studies in this domain should adopt both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection. Furthermore, future research should adopt a multilevel research design to enable investigation on the trends that might occur with time.

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